

Relationships between effect-based analysis, emerging pollutants, and conventional water quality parameters in a coastal aquifer

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Abstract

The presence of emerging contaminants (ECs) in groundwater reserves is a growing concern globally. Despite this reality, limited data exists describing EC-associated biological activity in aquifers and the associations between EC burdens and conventional water quality parameters including chemistry and microbiology. The Cape Flats Aquifer (CFA) is subject to various sources of contamination (industrial, residential, and agricultural). To better understand the spatiotemporal patterns within this area, an extensive water quality index (WQI) was developed, incorporating 24 parameters measured over 98 boreholes within a five-year period (2018 – 2021, and 2023). Upon the identification of several contamination hotspots, a battery of effect-based methods (EBMs) were applied to screen groundwater for endocrine disruptive (i.e., estrogenicity- and androgenicity), and aryl hydrocarbon receptor activation over two seasons. An *in vivo* fish embryo toxicity (FET) assay was furthermore applied to screen for embryotoxicity and teratogenicity. Analytical chemistry was performed in parallel with the EBMs to quantify a selection of ECs including pharmaceuticals, pesticides, and personal care products. A subsequent pollution source delineation principal component analysis (PCA) using the WQI parameters showed that a mix of agricultural, geogenic, and residential sources contribute to the poor water quality. Further information could be deduced with the incorporation of the EBMs data, where certain sites had significant endocrine disruptive potential. We conclude that caution should be taken when abstracting water from areas that were identified as pollution hotspots and that efforts should be taken in curtailing some of the activities contributing to the deteriorating groundwater quality. Finally, we show that EBMs can be a valuable tool in combination with traditional water parameters to provide a more comprehensive analysis of at-risk groundwater sources.